

Motivation and Morale: An Evaluation on the Impact of Reward Schemes on DA-PCC Employees' Behavior and Performance

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Proverbs 2:3-6: “Cries for insight and asks for understanding. Search for them as you would for silver; seek them like hidden treasures. Then you will understand what it means to fear the Lord, and you will gain knowledge of God. For the Lord grants wisdom! From his mouth come knowledge and understanding.” We are often encouraged to seek knowledge and wisdom. Research, in many ways, is a pursuit of this divine wisdom that God offers us. These verses remind us of the value of study and the pursuit of understanding as an act of honoring God.

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- The Researchers

DEDICATION

To all my beloved prayer warriors,

...this labor of love is devoted to you, with deepest gratitude and appreciation!

- The Researchers

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ABSTRACT

Any organization employing reward schemes can positively impact employee motivation and performance. When employees are motivated to work at higher levels of productivity, the organization as a whole will run more efficiently and effectively at reaching its goals. Reward schemes come in many forms, such as intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. Therefore, the organization must critically understand which reward schemes are most effective in motivating employees to perform at their best.

This study evaluates the impact of reward schemes on employee motivation and performance at the Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). The study aims to identify existing schemes, assess employee perceptions, and analyze how rewards influence productivity and work quality. The study included 30 permanent employees of the Philippine Carabao Centre (PCC) National Headquarters and Gene Pool at Science City Munoz, Nueva Ecija.

A descriptive quantitative approach was used, with surveys gathering data on employee experiences. The findings show that both intrinsic motivators—such as recognition and personal growth opportunities—and extrinsic factors, including salary, benefits, and job security, significantly influence employee engagement and organizational commitment. Demographic factors like age, tenure, and position also affect perceptions of reward schemes, highlighting the need for tailored approaches to improve effectiveness.

The study concludes that customized reward programs enhance employee satisfaction and performance. Recommendations include balancing monetary and non-monetary rewards, improving recognition efforts, and creating strategies that address diverse needs. This research provides a framework for optimizing reward schemes to foster a positive work environment, boost morale, and improve service delivery.

Keywords:- *Reward Schemes; Employee Motivation; Employee Performance; Employee Satisfaction.*

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *The Problem and its Background*

In today's workplace, aligning employee motivation and morale with organizational objectives is key to enhancing both behavior and performance. To achieve this, most business organizations use one type or another of reward schemes. The importance of reward schemes in promoting employee satisfaction and engagement is becoming more widely acknowledged. Reward systems, whether financial or non-financial, are increasingly seen as essential for promoting employee engagement and job satisfaction. Employees may be motivated to meet deadlines, establish and accomplish difficult goals, and continuously provide their best effort if they believe they will be rewarded.

According to a prior study, maintaining employee motivation is a critical component of human resources and management in organizations (Latham, 2012).

In addition, reward schemes, whether intrinsic or extrinsic, motivate employees (F Riasat, S Aslam, et. al, 2016). Intrinsic rewards, such as personal growth and job satisfaction, are inherently motivating. Extrinsic rewards, like bonuses, promotions, and benefits, are external incentives used to drive specific behaviors. Understanding the difference between intrinsic and extrinsic rewards is essential in facilitating the motivational aspects of employees. Organizations can establish a more effective work environment that fosters engagement and motivation by connecting both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards (Barber and

Bretz, 2000). Indeed, employee motivation, as a multidimensional construct influenced by a myriad of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, has become an important aspect that defines organizational success. This summary canvasses key theories, which explain the intricate relationship between rewards, recognition, and employee engagement.

According to that, the research theories utilized by the researcher address the department goals of The Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). This is because the success of DA-PCC relies highly on its employees' motivation and performance. Understanding how different types of rewards have an impact on motivation and morale is thus crucial to optimizing employee performance and achieving organizational goals. Hence, this research will examine how different reward schemes can affect an employee's behavior and performance in DA-PCC.

➤ *Literature Review*

This section presents the related literature and studies which provide background in the conceptualization of the study.

According to the study conducted by MHS Sayed et. al (2021), a motivated employee gives his/her optimum effort to improve firm performance (Dessler, Cole & Chhinzer, 2015). Also, a motivated employee expects that both the financial and non-financial rewards are aligned with their performance. Motivation includes various feelings that enable employees to consistently achieve assigned targets and goals (Baron, Rea & Daniels, 1992). Both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards can play a complementary role in motivating employees. While extrinsic rewards can provide an immediate boost or incentive to perform well, intrinsic rewards are often the key to long-term satisfaction and engagement. For example, an employee might feel motivated to achieve a sales target (extrinsic reward) because of the financial bonus offered. However, if they also find joy in helping clients and enjoy the process of closing deals (intrinsic reward), they may be more likely to consistently perform well, even after the bonus has been received.

Herzberg's (1959) Two-Factor Theory differentiates between intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, arguing that while extrinsic rewards (e.g., salary, job security) prevent dissatisfaction, intrinsic rewards (e.g., recognition, meaningful work) are essential for genuine job satisfaction. Supporting Herzberg's framework, Milkovich, Newman, and Gerhart (2013) highlight those financial rewards can enhance employee retention but may not sustain long-term engagement. Further research by Meyer and Allen (1991) expands this understanding by introducing the concept of organizational commitment. They argue that employees who receive regular, meaningful non-monetary rewards, such as career development opportunities, are more likely to develop a strong emotional bond with their organization. Additionally, Campbell (1990) demonstrated a positive correlation between performance-based incentives and productivity, particularly in organizations with transparent reward structures. This cumulative evidence underscores the multifaceted impact of both monetary and non-monetary rewards on employee behavior and performance. This distinction is echoed by Vroom's (1964) Expectancy Theory, which suggests that individuals are motivated by the belief that their efforts will lead to desirable rewards. Similarly, Adams (1963) focused on the concept of equity, proposing that employees' perceptions of fairness in reward distribution significantly influence their motivation and performance.

Maslow's (1943) Hierarchy of Needs provided a foundational understanding of how individuals prioritize needs, including both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, with self-actualization at the top. Building on Maslow's ideas, Locke and Latham (1990) introduced the Goal Setting Theory, asserting that specific and challenging goals, when combined with proper feedback, can significantly boost motivation and improve performance. Expanding on these theories, Meyer and Allen (1991) presented a Three-Component Model of Organizational Commitment, suggesting that affective commitment (emotional attachment to the organization) can be fostered through meaningful rewards. This model complements Campbell's (1990) findings, which showed a

strong correlation between performance-based incentives and employee productivity, especially when rewards are clear and aligned with employee expectations.

Milkovich, Newman, and Gerhart (2013) emphasized that financial compensation can improve employee retention, though it may not sustain motivation over time. In contrast, non-monetary rewards, such as career advancement and recognition, often yield longer-term commitment. Kuvaas et al. (2012) reinforced this by showing that employees with positive leader-member exchange relationships (built on social and intrinsic rewards) exhibited greater loyalty and performance.

Furthering this understanding, Dysvik and Kuvaas (2013) found that achievement-oriented employees are more responsive to intrinsic rewards, like opportunities for skill development, than to extrinsic rewards alone. This finding aligns with Deci, Koestner, and Ryan’s (1999) meta-analysis, which demonstrated that excessive reliance on extrinsic rewards can undermine intrinsic motivation, reducing engagement over time. Research by Klein, Molloy, and Brinsfield (2012) argued for a more nuanced view of workplace commitment, distinguishing between affective and calculative commitment. They highlight that commitment rooted in affective bonds tends to drive higher morale and performance, supporting Wright and Cropanzano’s (2000) study, which found that psychological well-being and job satisfaction strongly predict job performance.

In line with these findings, Morgeson and Humphrey (2006) developed the Work Design Questionnaire (WDQ), which assesses how job design elements (e.g., task variety, autonomy) influence motivation and satisfaction, suggesting that well-designed roles can enhance both morale and performance. Finally, Allen and Meyer’s (1996) examination of organizational commitment provide evidence that affective commitment, strengthened through rewards aligned with employee values, contributes significantly to employee loyalty and work quality.

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

Employee motivation is crucial for enhancing productivity, job satisfaction, and organizational success. This research is based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, developed by Frederick Herzberg in 1959, suggests that certain aspects of the work environment led to satisfaction (motivators), while others prevent dissatisfaction (hygiene factors). When considering **reward schemes**, the framework can be expanded by understanding how these rewards can directly influence both the **motivators** and **hygiene factors**, creating an environment that fosters engagement, productivity, and long-term commitment. According to Herzberg, job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not opposites, but distinct concepts. The hygiene factors (such as salary, working conditions, company policies) are essential for avoiding dissatisfaction, but they do not necessarily motivate employees. On the other hand, motivators (such as recognition, responsibility, personal growth) are intrinsic factors that lead to higher job satisfaction and motivation.

➤ *Theoretical Framework Model*

Fig 1 The Interaction between Hygiene Factors and Motivators on Employee Satisfaction and Motivation

➤ *Relationships between Hygiene Factors and Motivators*

- **Hygiene Factors** set the basic conditions necessary for employees to function effectively in their jobs. When hygiene factors are poorly managed, employees are more likely to be dissatisfied, disengaged, or demotivated.
- **Motivators**, however, directly influence how committed, engaged, and motivated employees feel about their work. Positive experiences with motivators contribute to higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation, which translate into better performance and organizational outcomes.

If hygiene factors are adequate but motivators are absent, employees will not experience deep satisfaction or high motivation, even if they are not dissatisfied.

➤ *Impact of Hygiene Factors on Job Satisfaction*

- **Low Hygiene:** When hygiene factors are subpar (e.g., poor compensation, ineffective policies, unsafe working conditions), employees experience dissatisfaction, which negatively affects their performance and job satisfaction.
- **High Hygiene:** Adequate hygiene factors prevent dissatisfaction but may not drive motivation. For example, competitive salaries and secure jobs prevent turnover and complaints, but they do not significantly boost morale.

➤ *Impact of Motivators on Job Motivation*

- **Presence of Motivators:** When employees are given opportunities for achievement, recognition, and personal growth, they experience intrinsic motivation, leading to increased job satisfaction, engagement, and higher performance.
- **Absence of Motivators:** When motivators are lacking, employees may feel stagnant, leading to lower job satisfaction and performance despite favorable hygiene factors.

➤ *Practical Implications for Organizations*

- **Focus on Hygiene Factors:** Organizations must ensure that basic work conditions are adequate to avoid dissatisfaction. Addressing complaints regarding pay, working conditions, and policies is essential for employee retention and stability.
- **Enhance Motivators:** Organizations should emphasize intrinsic motivators by creating opportunities for employees to achieve meaningful work, provide recognition for accomplishments, and offer chances for growth.
- **Customization:** A tailored approach is crucial—different employees may respond differently to motivators. For example, some may be driven by recognition, while others value career advancement or challenging tasks.

➤ *Reward Schemes Based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory*

Reward schemes refer to the structured incentives and recognition systems a company implements to motivate employees. Rewards can be financial (e.g., salary, bonuses, stock options) or non-financial (e.g., recognition programs, career development opportunities). Organizations should carefully design their reward schemes by addressing both motivators and hygiene factors to maximize employee satisfaction and motivation. A balanced approach can lead to long-term employee engagement and performance.

➤ *Motivators and Reward Schemes*

Reward schemes that directly influence the motivators include:

- **Recognition and Achievement:** Reward systems that acknowledge and celebrate employees' accomplishments contribute to a sense of achievement and recognition. Examples include awards, public recognition, employee of the month programs, or performance-based bonuses.
- **Opportunities for Growth and Advancement:** Reward schemes that offer career development opportunities, promotions, training programs, and mentorship align with Herzberg's motivators. Employees are motivated when they perceive a future of personal growth and career progression.
- **Responsibility and Autonomy:** Rewards in the form of greater responsibility, challenging assignments, or the ability to work independently can serve as powerful motivators. These rewards provide employees with a sense of ownership and control over their work.
- **Job Enrichment:** By enriching jobs and offering opportunities for employees to take on new, more challenging tasks, companies can align rewards with Herzberg's concept of meaningful work.

➤ *Hygiene Factors and Reward Schemes*

Reward schemes that influence hygiene factors focus on the extrinsic elements of the job environment. These factors are crucial for preventing dissatisfaction, though they do not inherently lead to higher job satisfaction.

- **Compensation and Benefits:** Salary, bonuses, and benefits packages are classic examples of hygiene factors. Fair and competitive compensation is essential for employees to feel that they are being treated fairly. If compensation is inadequate or perceived as unfair, dissatisfaction will arise, even if the other aspects of the job are satisfying.
- **Job Security:** A reward system that guarantees stability, such as long-term contracts, pension plans, and health benefits, directly impacts job security, a critical hygiene factor.
- **Work Environment and Conditions:** A well-structured reward system that ensures a safe, healthy, and supportive work environment (e.g., ergonomic workspaces, mental health programs, flexible work arrangements) contributes to overall satisfaction and minimizes dissatisfaction.
- **Interpersonal Relationships:** Reward schemes can influence team dynamics and work relationships. Offering team-building activities, social events, and fostering a culture of mutual respect and support can contribute to positive relationships among employees, reducing interpersonal conflict.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory provides a robust foundation for understanding job satisfaction and motivation. By integrating reward schemes that address both **motivators** and **hygiene factors**, organizations can create a work environment where employees feel valued, engaged, and motivated. A well-balanced reward system not only reduces dissatisfaction but also encourages higher levels of performance, productivity, and retention.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

The research theories utilized by the researcher address the department goals of The Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). This is because the success of DA-PCC relies highly on its employees' motivation and performance. Understanding how different types of rewards have an impact on motivation and morale is thus crucial to optimizing employee performance and achieving organizational goals. Hence, this research will examine how different reward schemes can affect an employee's behavior and performance in DA-PCC.

Specifically, the objectives of this study were the following:

- *To Determine the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Reward Schemes in Place at DA-PCC, in Terms of:*
 - ✓ Motivators (Intrinsic Factors)
 - ✓ Achievement
 - ✓ Recognition
 - ✓ The work itself
 - ✓ Responsibility
 - ✓ Opportunities for advancement
 - ✓ Personal growth
 - ✓ Hygiene Factors (Extrinsic Factors)
 - ✓ Employee Salary
 - ✓ Company Benefits
 - ✓ Employee Bonuses
 - ✓ Gratuity Pay
 - ✓ Company Policies
 - ✓ Supervision
 - ✓ Interpersonal relationships
 - ✓ Working conditions
 - ✓ Job Security
- *To assess the Effectiveness of Reward Schemes on the Motivation and Organizational Commitment of DA-PCC Employees, in Terms of:*
 - ✓ Employee Physiological Needs
 - ✓ Employee Safety and Security
 - ✓ Employee Organizational Belonginess
 - ✓ Employee Self-Esteem
 - ✓ Employee Self Actualization
- *To assess the Effectiveness of Reward Schemes on Productivity and the Quality of Work of DA-PCC Employees, in Terms of:*
 - ✓ Clarity
 - ✓ Challenge
 - ✓ Commitment
 - ✓ Feedback

✓ Complexity

- *To Determine how Demographic Factors (Age, Tenure, Position) affect DA-PCC Employees' Perceptions of Reward Schemes, in Terms of:*

- ✓ Personal Identity
- ✓ Social Identity
- ✓ Social Categorization
- ✓ Distinct Social Groups (Work Environment)

- *To propose and develop plan that shall guide DA-PCC in designing and implementing effective reward schemes, in terms of:*

- ✓ Financial Needs
- ✓ Emotional Needs
- ✓ Developmental Needs

By knowing how these incentives impact behaviors and performance, the PCC can develop more appropriate strategies in strengthening factors to encourage innovation, sustainability, and community influence. This will include recommendations for balancing monetary and non-monetary rewards, improving recognition programs, and tailoring reward schemes to diverse employee demographics and industry needs. The study's findings could provide a strategic framework for DA-PCC management in constructing a more operative reward program. Knowing specific employees' needs and preferences will enable building practical initiatives that not only enhance their motivation but also create a positive work environment. This is especially true in today's economy, where an employee's happiness is almost essential to holding them and also performing successfully as an organization.

➤ *Scope and Limitations of the Study*

The scope of this study encompasses an in-depth examination of the impact of reward schemes on permanent employees' motivation, morale and performance at Department of Agriculture – Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). Specifically, the research is focused to examine both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards mechanisms currently in place at the organization, determine the employees' perception of these rewards, and assess their effectiveness in enhancing the employees' motivation, organizational commitment, work quality, productivity and overall job performance. The research also examined the demographic characteristics of permanent employees' such age, gender, job role and tenure, to explore how these factors influence their response to the reward schemes of the organization. The research employs a quantitative approach to make sure an objective evaluation of the relationship between reward schemes and employee behavior.

However, this research is limited by exclusive focus on the Department of Agriculture – Philippine Carabao Center Headquarters, which may not fully represent the experiences and perspective of employees in other regions or branches of the Department of Agriculture. The findings are also specific to the organizational culture, and reward schemes at DA-PCC, limiting their applicability to other sectors or organizations. In addition, this research is confined to permanent employees, excluding contract of service (COS) or temporary employees, whose motivations and morale may differ. These factors could affect the generalizability of the research's conclusion to the broader employee population or other government agencies and industries.

➤ *Significance of the Study*

This study may be beneficial to the following stakeholders:

- **DA-PCC Management and Leadership:** As a result of this study, the organization shall be in a better position to understand the influence of reward schemes on employee motivation and morale. The management may customize incentive programs to meet the expectations of employees and organizational objectives by determining which types of rewards effectively improve employee behavior and performance. Consequently, this may result in increased output, less employee attrition, and enhanced organizational efficiency.
- **Human Resource (HR) Professionals:** The results of the study can help the HR division develop and enhance policies, employee engagement plans, and incentive schemes. Understanding which reward schemes have the most impact on employee morale and performance can help to optimize HR processes, resulting in increased employee retention, satisfaction, and overall well-being.
- **Employees of DA-PCC:** Employees will gain indirectly from this study since it may result in more tailored and effective reward schemes. Understanding how reward systems influence motivation and job performance may enable them to offer feedback to the management, encouraging a more collaborative work environment and improving job satisfaction.
- **Policymakers and Organizational Researchers:** The study will add to the corpus of research on performance, morale, and motivation at work. Important information will be discovered by researchers and policymakers that may be utilized to create more successful reward schemes for DA-PCC as well as other public and commercial organizations.

- **Future Researchers:** This study will be useful for scholars, academicians, and students interested in organizational behavior, human resource management, and motivation theory. The findings can serve as a foundation for future research, case studies, and practical applications in corporate management and organizational development courses.
- **External Stakeholders (Investors and Donors):** Donors and investors, among other external stakeholders, will learn more about how DA-PCC operates internally. A motivated and high-performing workforce is typically a significant aspect in an organization's success, and this study will show how well-implemented reward systems can contribute to long-term organizational growth and stability while favorably affecting investment decisions.
- **Definition of Terms** To facilitate better understanding, the following key terms were defined conceptually or operationally:
 - **Achievement.** The sense of accomplishment employees gains from completing meaningful tasks or goals.
 - **Challenge.** The level of difficulty in tasks that encourages growth and improved performance.
 - **Clarity.** The clear communication of goals and processes to ensure understanding and alignment.
- **Commitment.** Employee dedication to achieving organizational goals and remaining engaged.
- **Company Benefits.** Non-monetary incentives supporting employee well-being, such as health insurance and paid leave.
- **Company Policies.** Established guidelines governing workplace operations and behavior to ensure fairness.
- **Complexity.** The degree of intricacy in tasks or processes that can impact employee engagement.
- **Contract of Service Employees.** Workers hired on a fixed-term basis without regular employment benefits.
- **Demographic Factors.** Characteristics like age, tenure, and position affect perceptions and behaviors.
- **Department of Agriculture – Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC).** A government agency focused on carabao-based rural development.
- **Developmental Needs.** Opportunities for skill enhancement and career growth to foster employee commitment.
- **Distinct Social Groups.** Specific employee categories with unique needs and preferences in the workplace.
- **Emotional Needs.** Psychological support through recognition and positive workplace relationships.
- **Employee Behavior.** Actions and attitudes of employees influenced by workplace factors.
- **Employee Bonuses.** Financial incentives provided for meeting or exceeding performance targets.
- **Employee Morale.** The overall mood and satisfaction level of employees in the workplace.
- **Employee Motivation.** The drive to achieve goals and perform effectively in their roles.
- **Employee Self-Actualization.** Realization of one's potential through personal and professional growth.
- **Employee Self-Esteem.** Confidence and self-worth derived from recognition and achievements.
- **Employee Safety and Security.** Assurance of a safe working environment and stable employment.
- **Employee Salary.** Monetary compensation provided for work performed.
- **Employee Satisfaction.** The contentment employees feel about their job roles and rewards.
- **Employee Organizational Belongingness.** A sense of connection and value within the organization.
- **Employee Physiological Needs.** Basic requirements like financial stability and well-being.
- **Employee Performance.** The effectiveness and quality of employees' work.
- **Extrinsic Rewards.** External incentives such as salary, bonuses, and benefits.
- **Feedback.** Information provided to employees about their performance to encourage improvement.
- **Financial Needs.** Monetary requirements for stability and satisfaction in life and work.
- **Gratuity Pay.** Additional compensation for long service or exceptional performance.
- **Goal-Setting Theory.** A theory suggesting that specific, challenging goals improve performance.
- **Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory.** A theory distinguishing factors that prevent dissatisfaction from those that promote satisfaction.
- **High Hygiene.** Adequate extrinsic factors like salary and policies that prevent dissatisfaction.
- **Hygiene Factors.** External job conditions necessary to avoid dissatisfaction but not to motivate.
- **Interpersonal Relationships.** Workplace interactions that foster collaboration and morale.
- **Job Security.** Assurance of stable employment and reliable income.
- **Intrinsic Rewards.** Internal motivators like personal growth and job satisfaction.
- **Low Hygiene.** Insufficient external factors leading to dissatisfaction.
- **Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs.** A theory outlining five levels of human needs from basic to self-actualization.
- **Monetary Rewards.** Financial incentives, such as salary and bonuses.
- **Motivators.** Intrinsic factors like recognition and responsibility that promote job satisfaction
- **Non-Monetary Rewards.** Incentives like recognition and development opportunities that do not involve money.
- **Recognition.** Acknowledgment of employees' efforts and achievements.
- **Responsibility.** The sense of ownership employees feels in their roles.

- **Reward Schemes.** Structured systems to incentivize and recognize employee performance.
- **Social Categorization.** Grouping employees based on roles or other characteristics.
- **Social Identity.** A sense of belonging to a group based on shared traits or roles.
- **Social Identity Theory.** A theory explaining how group memberships influence self-concept and behavior.
- **Supervision.** Managerial support and guidance to help employees achieve goals.
- **Opportunities for Advancement.** Career progression options like promotions or training.
- **Organizational Commitment.** Employees' emotional attachment and dedication to their workplace.
- **Permanent Employees.** Workers with stable, long-term employment and benefits.
- **Personal Identity.** Unique values and goals shaping how employees view rewards and roles.

- **Personal Growth.** Development of skills and potential through learning and challenges.
- **Productivity.** The efficiency and output of employees' work.
- **Quality of Work.** The standard of outcomes delivered by employees.
- **The Work Itself.** The intrinsic value and satisfaction derived from performing job tasks.

CHAPTER TWO METHODS AND PROCEDURES

This chapter presents the research design, locale of the study, respondents, sample and sampling procedure, instruments, data gathering procedures, data analysis techniques and ethical concerns to determine, assess, and evaluate the impact of reward schemes on DA-PCC employees' behavior and performance.

➤ *Research Design*

This study employed the descriptive research design. According to Best (1963), this research design is further concerned with the conditions or relationships that exist; practices that prevail; and beliefs and processes that are going on; effects that are being felt or trends that are developing.

This design was appropriate because of the study's purpose to determine the intrinsic and extrinsic reward schemes in place, assess the impact and effectiveness of varying reward schemes on the employees' motivation, organizational commitment, productivity, and quality of work at the Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). Through this research design, respondents' demographic profiles were garnered on top of the examination of the effectiveness of the rewards schemes on the motivation, organizational commitment, productivity, and quality of work of the selected respondents from the DA-PCC. In this research, the socio-demographic variables, the types of reward schemes, employee motivation, and performance survey scores of permanent DA-PCC employees were utilized.

➤ *Locale of the Study*

The research site for this study was the Philippine Carabao Center (PCC) National Headquarters and Gene Pool, located in the Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The Philippine Carabao Center (PCC), an attached agency of the Department of Agriculture (DA), was created by virtue of Republic Act 7307 in 1992. PCC became operational in 1993, taking momentum from the gains and achievements of earlier programs.

This facility served as the central hub for PCC's nationwide efforts in carabao conservation, genetic improvement, and livestock research. It housed various departments dedicated to research, administration, training, and extension services, which work collaboratively to promote sustainable livestock production and to support the livelihood of Filipino farmers.

As the primary facility of PCC, the National Headquarters and Gene Pool was equipped with advanced resources and specialized personnel, making it an ideal setting to assess the effects of reward schemes on employee motivation and performance within a high-impact agricultural organization.

Fig 2 Map Location of DA-PCC

Fig 3 DA-PCC Infrastructures

➤ *Respondents of the Study*

This study involved thirty (30) permanent employees of the Department of Agriculture-Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC).

Focusing on permanent employees assured that the respondents will hold a stable and relatively long-term view of DA-PCC's reward practices, thereby providing insight into the immediate and the cumulative impacts of various incentive schemes. As the primary stakeholders, understanding the impact that reward schemes have on motivation, morale, behavior, and performance within the organization is vital for these individuals. The study focused on this specific population as a way of getting an all-rounded experience and perception regarding monetary and non-monetary rewards and their effects on work satisfaction and engagement.

Given the DA-PCC’s mission of sustainable livestock development and the role that employees play in achieving organizational goals, it is essential to understand how reward structures support or challenge their motivation and commitment to their roles. Including only permanent employees helps control for variables such as job security and stability, which may affect responses and outcomes differently for non-permanent employees. This approach also enhances the relevance of the findings to DA-PCC’s HR and administrative policies, providing valuable feedback for potential enhancements to reward structures that could improve overall employee performance and organizational efficiency.

Table 1 Respondents’ Years of Experience

Tenure	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	5	16.7%
4-6 years	4	13.3%
7+ years	21	70%
Total	30	100%

Presented on Table 1 is the distribution of the respondents according to their tenure in DA-PCC. The majority of the respondents were at 7+ years of service (f=21, %=70%), which implies that the company works well in preserving their employees for a long period of time.

➤ *Sample and Sampling Procedure*

The sample was composed of respondents gathered from the employee population of the DA-PCC. The study based its roster on the employee database of the Human Resource Management department. To identify potential participants, the researcher first accessed a comprehensive list of all permanent employees through the Human Resource Management Information System (HRMIS). This system provides up-to-date information on employee status, roles, and tenure within the organization.

Convenience sampling was utilized in selecting the appropriate sample size for the researcher. This non-probability sampling technique involves picking participants who are most accessible and willing to participate in this study. This approach was considered feasible for this research and opened up the DA-PCC employees who avowed that they are available and willing to participate in this research. Additional considerations, such as ensuring departments, roles, and seniority, were made to ensure that the sample was reflective of the broader employee population. Subsequently, the sampling procedure was used due to limited financial resources, available time for gathering data, and difficulty of locating the respondents.

➤ *Research Instruments*

In order to gather the study's necessary data for its completion, the researchers utilized a survey questionnaire that was administered through the use of digital platform. A combination of Open-ended and Closed-ended questions, Likert scale questions, and demographic questions were used in the survey in order to obtain a detailed impression of the respondents.

Specifically, data were collected using Google Form survey questionnaire from a group of respondents consists of permanent DA-PCC employees. The questions were structured in a Likert-type scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). There are 4 items intended to determine demographic information like age, gender, job position, and tenure (length of employment). This study used frequency counts, percentages, and averages for descriptive statistics.

- **Preliminary Part.** It comprised of a brief letter of acknowledgement, an overview of what the survey is about, it's objectives and assurance that responses will be kept confidential, and the data will only be used for the purpose of this study. It also included the respondents Demographic Information. The respondents filled out the instrument.
- **Part I** contained items to gather data that determined the types of reward schemes currently employed by DA-PCC. It includes questions, generally divided in two sections, which are Motivators (Intrinsic Factors) and Hygiene Factors (Extrinsic Factors). Each included the key variables which were relevant to this study based on the reading from published studies.
- **Part II** contained items to gather data that assessed the effectiveness of reward schemes on the motivation and organizational commitment of DA-PCC employees. It includes questions, generally divided in five sections: Employee Physiological Needs, Employee Safety and Security, Employee Organizational Belongingness, Employee Self-Esteem and Employee Self-Actualization.
- **Part III** contained items to gather data that assessed the effectiveness of reward schemes on productivity and the quality of work of DA-PCC employees. It includes questions, generally divided between Clarity and Challenge in Reward Schemes, Commitment and Feedback in Reward Schemes, and Complexity and Work Quality in Reward Schemes.
- **Part IV** contained items to gather data that determine how demographic factors affect DA-PCC employees' perceptions of reward schemes. It includes questions, generally divided amongst employee Personal Identity, Social Identity, Social Categorization, and Distinct Social Groups (Work Environment).
- **Part V** contained items that gathered employees' feedbacks and recommendations that shall guide DA-PCC in designing and implementing effective reward schemes. This part was made up of the combination of checklist and open-ended questions.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments, these underwent the professionals' review in the field of human resources and research. After the consultation, the comments, suggestions, and recommendations were merged into the instrument for revisions. Through these validity and reliability measures, the study anticipates a valid and reliable set of results that correctly portrays the experiences of permanent employees in DA-PCC's reward schemes.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedures*

The researchers' data collection procedure in this study involved systematic approaches, structured within a defined protocol, as outlined below:

Initially, prior to the data gathering process, the researchers drafted a formal request letter seeking permission to conduct the survey. This letter signed by both the researchers and their course adviser, is addressed to the head of the DA-PCC agency, to authorize the study.

Upon approval of the request to conduct data gathering, the researchers developed the self-made survey questionnaire and any information received back during the experts' review of the questionnaire, modifications were made to the contents of the questionnaire for clarity purposes as well as interrelated changes. Before the survey, a brief invitation note was provided to the respondents, explaining the purpose of the study and highlighting the importance of their participation. They were also assured that their responses would remain confidential.

After that, the researchers administered the survey through digital platform to the targeted respondents, the permanent employees in DA-PCC. Considering the likely low response rate commonly associated with cross-sectional surveys, the survey link was sent to the picked respondents' email address and other internal communication channels that are common to members of the organization.

Period for data collection was set and respondents were respectfully asked to complete the survey. Follow-ups were done to increase the response rate, by sending messages to the employees to complete the questionnaires. After the data gathering period, the responses were gathered and kept in the most secure manner possible for analysis. Data gathered were sent to the hired Statistician for data analysis and interpretation. Subsequently, these developed structured data collection procedures generated an understanding of the experiences of permanent employees in DA-PCC's reward schemes.

➤ *Data Analysis Techniques*

The analytics method used and is applicable to this study's research questions is the descriptive quantitative analysis. This analyzed the survey responses from selected permanent employees in DA-PCC. This method is suitable for use as it allows the researchers to analyze numerical results, and identify the trends of respondents' experiences and perceptions of the reward schemes on employee motivation, morale and job performance.

The survey data were collected and arranged for analysis through the statistical aid of SPSS which stands for Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. In as much as quantitative data were use, the descriptive analysis was used in order to analyze the data by using means, median, mode and frequency tables, and percentages. By utilizing this statistical method, the study is able to analyze key trends in the most significant areas, including demographic factors, motivators and hygiene factors, motivation and organizational commitment, as well as productivity and work quality among DA-PCC employees within the context of reward schemes.

➤ *Ethical Concerns*

In this study, several factors were taken into consideration to act as guidelines in handling the participants more especially on ethical considerations. First, only participants willing to participate were engaged. Each participant was given an acknowledgement or consent letter attached with the questionnaire, that described the research in detail. Through this, the participants were clearly informed of what their participation involves. The participants also received information concerning the study's objectives, methods, anticipated risks and benefits for the participants who are involved in the study. They were also informed that they can quit from the study at any time.

Second, optional anonymity was enforced; participants were given the option not to identify themselves and any data identifying them will be removed from the survey results, and stored and processed under robust security procedures to preserve the participant's anonymity throughout the study. All collected data were stored in a password controlled files and were used for this research only. To minimize risk to participants, the study guarantees that no respondent identification data will be connected to the study data.

Third, the emotional experiences of participants were taken cared of because some of them may share intimate experiences. Respondents were assured that their responses were not disclosed in any way and that their opinion will be valued. Finally, engaging in this study was voluntary such that participants were informed that they can freely decline to participate without punishing consequences. This conforms to ethical standards provide a good atmosphere in dealing with respondents to a level that no any physical or psychological harm come to the respondents hence increasing the validity of the research.

CHAPTER THREE PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the findings obtained from the primary instrument used in the evaluation on the impact of reward schemes on DA-PCC employees’ behavior and performance. The responses were organized, quantified, and interpreted using the applicable statistical tools. The presentation observed the sequence of the specific problems formulated in this study.

A. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The distribution and demographic profile of the respondents was described in terms of age, gender, role or job position, and tenure with the organization.

➤ *Respondents According to their Age*

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents According to their Age

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	20-30	4	13.3%
	31-40	13	43.3%
	41-50	11	36.7%
	51+	2	6.7%
	Total	30	100%

The provided data reveals a significant concentration of individuals within the 31-40 age group, comprising 43% of the total sample. This demographic likely represents individuals in the prime of their careers, potentially contributing to a higher level of experience and expertise within the group. The 41-50 age group, while slightly smaller, still constitutes a substantial portion at 37%. It could bring together valuable experience and zeal for work, thereby stabilizing the workforce. On the other hand, the percentages of 20-30 and 51+ age groups are much smaller, at 11% and 5%, respectively. The 20-30 age group may not be highly experienced but will carry with it a refreshing perspective and bright ideas. While the 51+ age group is very experienced and can contribute rich insight and advice to the junior members of the team.

➤ *Respondents According to their Gender*

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents According to their Gender

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Female	16	53.3%
	Male	14	46.7%
	Total	30	100%

Gender in the data is at near-even gender distribution. Females dominate with 53% whereas males have 47%. A balanced distribution suggests a range of perspectives and experiences in the group. It should also be noted that gender is one factor that influences behavior or attitudes, but one should not generalize too much. Individual variation in both gender groups would likely be major.

➤ *Respondents According to their Position*

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents According to their Position

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Administrative	6	20%
	Administrative, Research, Extension Service	1	3.3%
	Administrative, Technical, Extension Service	2	6.7%
	Administrative, Technical, Research, Extension Service	1	3.3%
	Extension Service	2	6.7%
	Knowledge Management	1	3.3%
	Research	10	33.3%
	Technical	6	20.0%
	Technical, Research, Extension Service	1	3.3%
	Total	30	100%

In the presented data, there is a visible spread of job design in the organization, with both Research and Technical kinds representing the highest possible positions, 33.3% and 20% respectively. This reflects an emphasis on research and technological inputs into the organization. Although not as expansive, administrative jobs also occupy 20% of the positions, implying the wide

role of administrative functions in supporting organizational effectiveness. The remaining positions, such as Extension Service, Knowledge Management, and combinations of these, indicate a scope more expansive than just activities and commitment to disseminate knowledge and practical application.

Of course, the delineation of roles may also depend on the particular aims and objectives of an organization. A greater concern for research and technical roles might indicate a focus upon innovation and development, while an administrative component is stronger may suggest a focus on operational efficiency, plus compliance with laws and regulations.

➤ *Respondents According to their Tenure*

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents According to their Tenure

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	1-3 years	4	13.3%
	4-6 years	4	13.3%
	7+ years	22	70%
	Total	30	100%

Evidence shows that 70% of the employees were part of the organization for 7 or more years, which means a large number of employees stay with the company for a long time. This could be a sign of organizational culture, because most employees have deep institutional knowledge, have strong relationships, and a high level of commitment towards the organization. However, it's worth noting that a significant portion of the workforce has been with the company for less than 7 years. While this could be attributed to various factors, such as recent hiring or turnover, it's important to consider the impact on organizational knowledge and experience. A balance between experienced and newer employees can be beneficial, as it can foster innovation, fresh perspectives, and continuity.

B. Rewards Schemes Implemented at DA-PCC

The following data determined the intrinsic and extrinsic reward schemes in place at DA-PCC.

➤ *Intrinsic Motivators (Intrinsic Factors)*

Table 6 Intrinsic Motivators

	N	Mean
1. I feel that DA-PCC provides rewards that recognize my personal achievements and accomplishments at work.	30	3.87
2. I regularly receive recognition for my contributions (e.g., an employee of the month, appreciation from supervisors or colleagues).	30	3.30
3. The tasks and responsibilities assigned to me are rewarding and contribute to my job satisfaction.	30	3.90
4. I am given enough responsibility in my role, and this sense of ownership motivates me to perform at my best.	30	4.10
5. I am offered opportunities for career advancement and professional development at DA-PCC.	30	3.93
6. DA-PCC provides rewards or opportunities that contribute to my personal growth (e.g., training, new skills development).	30	4.17
Aggregate Mean	30	3.88

The data indicates that DA-PCC employees generally perceive a positive impact of reward schemes on their motivation and job satisfaction (Martin & Uribe, 2021). The average mean rating of 3.88 across all statements suggests a moderate to high level of satisfaction with the current reward system. Specifically, employees seem to appreciate the opportunities for personal and professional growth offered by DA-PCC. Statements related to recognition, responsibility, and career advancement received particularly high ratings, indicating that these factors are important drivers of employee motivation. The current recognition for contributions, however, could be improved. Employees generally feel valued, but there are some areas where recognizing practices can be enhanced, such as developing more frequent and personalized recognition programs. Overall, the data shows that a well-designed reward system can significantly impact employee motivation and job satisfaction. While continuously investing in development, recognizing achievement, and providing development opportunities, DA-PCC can further enhance employee engagement and productivity.

➤ *Hygiene Factors (Extrinsic Factors)*

Table 7 Hygiene Factors

	N	Mean
1. My salary is competitive and reflective of my role and responsibilities at DA-PCC.	30	3.50
2. DA-PCC provides adequate employee benefits (e.g., health insurance, retirement plans, paid leave) that meet my needs.	30	3.93
3. I receive performance-based bonuses or other types of monetary incentives for meeting or exceeding work targets.	30	3.93
4. I am given gratuity or additional compensation for long service or excellent performance.	30	3.77
5. I believe that DA-PCC’s company policies are fair and transparent, contributing to a positive work environment.	30	3.60
7. The relationships I have with colleagues and supervisors are positive, respectful, and contribute to a supportive work environment.	29	3.83
8. The physical working conditions (e.g., office space, equipment, facilities) are comfortable and conducive to performing my job effectively.	30	3.77
9. I feel secure in my job, and DA-PCC offers stability in my employment.	30	4.00
Aggregate Mean	29	3.79

The data are indicative of a good impression from the working environment as viewed by the DA-PCC employees, and that compensation and benefits package is satisfactory. High average ratings to statements associated with salary, benefits, and job security-and work relationship suggest employees value being cared for by the organization. But at the same time, the performance-related incentives and gratuities still leave much to be desired. While employees may think their salaries are good and their benefits are sufficient, they would desire recognition and reward for outstanding performance and long-term service (Amushila & Bussin, 2021). DA-PCC can improve employee satisfaction and motivation through a stronger performance reward system and more bonuses that solicit an increase in great performance, recognition, and reward for long service.

C. *Reward Schemes on Motivation and Organizational Commitment at DA-PCC*

The following data assessed the effectiveness of reward schemes on the motivation and organizational commitment of DA-PCC employees.

➤ *Employee Physiological Needs*

Table 8 Employees’ Physiological Needs

	N	Mean
1. The current reward schemes provided by DA-PCC meet my basic financial needs (salary, allowances, etc.).	29	3.83
2. I feel that the rewards provided by DA-PCC adequately support my overall well-being and daily life.	29	3.48
Aggregate Mean	29	3.66

The data suggests that employees in the DA-PCC generally rated their current financial needs as adequately met with a mean rating of 3.83. However, when considering the rewards to support overall well-being and daily life, respondents rate their satisfaction slightly lower at 3.48. Although the employees are sated with their current salaries and allowances, there is always more to be done so that they are able to lead relatively better lives. For this purpose, employee benefits may include health, pension schemes, workplace welfare schemes, or professional development schemes (Martir & Uribe, 2021). Thus, DA-PCC may analyze employees’ needs thoroughly to pinpoint areas where support is needed further enhance their satisfaction. So, DA-PCC may analyze employees’ needs more thoroughly to pinpoint areas where support is needed in more detail to further enhance their satisfaction. This may involve questionnaires, focus groups, or interviews with employees to seek their direct feedback.

➤ *Employee Safety and Security*

Table 9 Employees’ Safety and Security

	N	Mean
1. The rewards offered by DA-PCC contribute to my job security and long-term career stability.	29	3.69
2. I feel secure in my current position due to the reward system in place at DA-PCC.	30	3.50
Aggregate Mean	29	3.60

The data suggests that employees in the DA-PCC moderately agree that the rewards system at DA-PCC contributes positively to their job security and long-term career stability. A mean rating of 3.69 suggests that most respondents view the rewards system favorably in terms of providing stability, but it may not be a strong or overwhelming feeling. employees moderately agree (with a mean rating of 3.50) that the reward system contributes to their sense of security in their current role. It is a bit lower than the

previous statement, meaning that while the reward system is seen as somewhat reassuring, it does not strongly influence their sense of security in the job. The aggregate mean rating of 3.60 means that employees have a generally positive but not extremely strong perception of how the rewards system contributes to their job security and stability. It reflects a moderate level of agreement that the rewards system plays a role in their job security.

➤ *Employee Self-Esteem*

Table 10 Employees’ Self-Esteem

	N	Mean
1. The reward schemes at DA-PCC positively affect my self-esteem and sense of accomplishment	29	3.66
2. The rewards I receive make me feel that my work is truly appreciated and recognized by the organization.	29	3.62
Aggregate Mean	29	3.64

It can be seen that on average, DA-PCC employees believe that reward schemes positively affect their self-esteem and appreciation for accomplishments. In other words, the average mean rating of 3.64 indicated an average level of satisfaction with the way in which rewards contributed to self-worth and appreciation. Furthermore, they feel that their work is appreciated and valued, and this enhances self-esteem. However, there is the possibility of further development of this dimension in the reward system, such as more tailor-made recognition programs or involvement in the display of such achievements by employees (Gagné et al., 2022). To build up employee self-confidence further, DA-PCC could strive for a positive incentive culture where employees are continually acknowledged for what they do and contribute. Providing opportunities for professional development and growth can thus empower employees and give them confidence in their capabilities.

➤ *Employee Organizational Belongingness*

Table 11 Employee Organizational Belongingness

	N	Mean
1. The reward schemes at DA-PCC make me feel valued as an employee and part of the team	30	3.55
2. I feel that the rewards I receive from DA-PCC help foster a sense of belonging to the organization.	30	3.72
Aggregate Mean	30	3.64

The data reveals that, on average, DA-PCC employees feel that reward schemes positively affect their organizational belonging. The average mean rating is 3.64, which represents a moderate level of satisfaction as to how rewards contribute to their organizational affiliation. Employees feel valued and considered part of the team, and rewards they obtain help promote a sense of belonging. Such positive perception about the culture and values by the organization will benefit in employees' engagement and, in turn, retention (Kurdi et al., 2020). DA-PCC may further enhance the feeling of belongingness in employees through team-building activities, social events, and cross-functional collaboration opportunities, as well as recognizing team achievements toward fostering collective feelings of accomplishment and strengthening organizational culture.

➤ *Employee Self-Actualization*

Table 12 Employees’ Self-Actualization

	N	Mean
1. DA-PCC’s reward schemes provide me with opportunities for personal growth and professional development.	30	3.67
2. The reward system at DA-PCC encourages me to strive for excellence and reach my full potential.	30	3.83
Aggregate Mean	30	3.75

From the data, it is found that DA-PCC employees view positive satisfaction due to the reward schemes in relation to their self-actualization. The average mean rating of 3.75 points to a fair degree of satisfaction regarding how rewards contribute to personal and professional growth. According to employees, the reward system has a motivational impact on them to strive for excellence and to reach the potential of perfection (Kiral, 2020). This positive perception can greatly influence employee motivation, engagement, and job satisfaction. To further enhance the self-actualization of employees, DA-PCC may consider a comprehensive career development program incorporating opportunities for training, mentoring, and coaching. Challenging assignments and recognition and rewarding innovative ideas could empower and motivate the employees to reach their full potential.

D. Reward Schemes on Employee Performance, Productivity and Work Quality at DA-PCC

The following data assessed the effectiveness of reward schemes on productivity and the quality of work of DA-PCC.

➤ *Clarity and Reward Schemes*

Table 13 Clarity and Reward Schemes

	N	Mean
1. The criteria for earning rewards within the DA-PCC organization is clear.	30	3.23
2. I often receive clear and detailed communication about available rewards and the processes.	30	3.00
Aggregate Mean	30	3.12

The data will then show that although the employees at DA-PCC are generally aware of the criteria for earning rewards, there is probably scope for improvement on the clarity and communication aspects related to reward processes. An average mean rating of 3.12 indicates moderate satisfaction as far as the clarity of reward schemes is concerned. For a clearer and easier understanding, DA-PCC could come up with a formulated reward policy that focuses on clear eligibility standards or criteria, performance metrics, and reward distribution procedures. This policy should be communicated well with all employees so as to understand expectations and requirements for the rewards to be earned (Ryan, 2023). More importantly, DA-PCC can hold regular and broader training and workshops on the reward policies and procedures to answer most of the workers' doubts or questions. By making the reward schemes clearer and more transparent, DA-PCC can better motivate and satisfy its employees.

➤ *Challenge and Reward Schemes*

Table 14 Challenge and Reward Schemes

	N	Mean
1. The tasks associated with qualifying for rewards is challenging.	30	3.70
2. In your opinion, do the reward schemes push you to strive for better performance and higher productivity?	30	3.77
Aggregate Mean	30	3.74

Data reveals that although the DA-PCC employees view the tasks related to qualifying for rewards as tough, they also believe that such toughness makes them work harder for better performance and higher productivity. The moderate mean rating of 3.74 would indicate a close enough level of motivation and engagement. The challenging nature of the tasks could be seen as a positive aspect due to stimulating growth, learning, and innovation. However, balancing those challenges with adequate support and resources is a responsibility, especially to avoid burnout and demotivation (Mone & London, 2020). DA-PCC may consider some strategies providing employees with the right amount of training, mentorship, and tools to overcome reward schemes-related challenges successfully. But by rewarding effort and improvement, even in the face of challenges, the organization can encourage employees and build a high-performance culture.

➤ *Commitment to the Reward System*

Table 15 Commitment to the Reward System

	N	Mean
1. I am committed in achieving the goals set within the reward scheme.	30	3.90
2. The reward schemes often encourage you to focus on my work and remain motivated.	30	3.77
Aggregate Mean	30	3.84

The data shows that DA-PCC employees are highly committed toward achieving the goals intended within the reward scheme. There is an average mean rating of 3.84 to verify the degree of motivation and engagement. Employees perceive that this campaign encourages them toward job focus and being motivated (Reeves et al., 2021). This can get highly converted into positive contributions toward productivity, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance. DA-PCC may also engage in a system of regular feedback and recognition to further deepen the commitment of employees. The organization can help employees stay on track, and become conscious of areas to improve by giving them prompt and constructive feedback. Moreover, rewarding the accomplishments of an individual or team can inspire employees further and further channel their energy toward organizational goals.

➤ *Feedback and its Impact*

Table 16 Feedback and its Impact

	N	Mean
1. I often receive feedback regarding my progress toward earning rewards.	30	2.90
2. Does the feedback from your supervisors or peers motivate you to perform better and aim for higher rewards?	30	3.50
Aggregate Mean	30	3.20

The frequency and quality of feedback that DA-PCC employees receive warrants improvement as the general perception on the received feedback was encouraging, though there is room for improvement. In the average mean rating case, the ratings scored an average mean of 3.20 against satisfaction level concerning the feedback system. In addition, although employees react to the feedback they receive as motivating, they may want more-frequent and specific feedback about their performance and their progress toward reward goals (Gnepp et al., 2020).

That may translate into one-on-one meetings with supervisors on a regular basis, formal performance reviews, and casual check-in sessions. To increase feedback effectiveness, DA-PCC should introduce a formal feedback system that clearly indicates expectations, holds regular sessions for check-ins, and gives constructive criticism. The performance management software or simply conducting the performance reviews can be some of the tools that help DA-PCC convey timely, specific, and actionable feedback about employees' performance. This will help them better accomplish their goals and feel more motivated and engaged.

➤ *Complexity of Reward Schemes*

Table 17 Complexity of Reward Schemes

	N	Mean
1. The reward schemes in DA-PCC are complex in terms of eligibility and earning rewards.	30	3.60
2. The complexity of the reward schemes hinders my ability to perform at my best.	30	2.70
Aggregate Mean	30	3.15

The data suggests that while DA-PCC employees perceive the reward schemes as somewhat complex, they also recognize that these complexities can hinder their ability to perform at their best. The average mean rating of 3.15 indicates a moderate level of concern regarding the complexity of the reward system. While complexity can add a level of challenge and motivation, it is important to ensure that the reward schemes are clear, transparent, and easy to understand. Overly complex schemes can lead to confusion, frustration, and decreased motivation. To address this issue, DA-PCC may consider simplifying the reward system by clarifying eligibility criteria, streamlining processes, and providing clear communication about the requirements for earning rewards. Additionally, offering training and support to employees can help them navigate the complexities of the system and focus on their work (Mızrak, 2024).

➤ *Impact of Reward Schemes on Work Quality and Productivity*

Table 18 Impact of Reward Schemes on Work Quality and Productivity

	N	Mean
1. The reward schemes improve the quality and overall productivity of my work.	30	3.47
2. Would you say that the complexity of the reward scheme has led to more efficient work practices in your department?	29	3.28
Aggregate Mean	29	3.38

The data suggests that DA-PCC employees perceive a positive impact of reward schemes on their work quality and productivity. The average mean rating of 3.38 indicates a moderate level of satisfaction with the effectiveness of the reward system in driving performance. Employees believe that the reward schemes motivate them to improve their work quality and productivity (Manzoor et al., 2021). However, the complexity of the reward schemes may have a mixed impact on work practices. While some employees may find that the complexity drives efficiency, others may experience challenges in navigating the system. To maximize the positive impact of reward schemes on work quality and productivity, DA-PCC may consider simplifying the reward system, providing clear guidance, and offering training to help employees understand the requirements and benefits. Additionally, recognizing and rewarding specific behaviors and outcomes that contribute to improved quality and productivity can further motivate employees to strive for excellence.

E. Demographic Factors' affect on Perceptions of Rewards Scheme at DA-PCC

The following data determined how demographic factors (age, tenure, position) affect DA-PCC employees' perceptions of reward schemes.

➤ *Personal Identity*

Table 19 Personal Identity

	N	Mean
1. My personal values and career stage influence how I view the rewards provided by DA-PCC (e.g., monetary vs. non-monetary rewards).	29	3.66
2. The reward schemes at DA-PCC align with my personal priorities, such as work-life balance or financial security.	30	3.20
Aggregate Mean	29	3.43

The data suggests that DA-PCC employees perceive a moderate level of alignment between the reward schemes and their personal values and career stage. The average mean rating of 3.43 indicates that while employees generally feel that the reward schemes are relevant to their individual needs, there may be opportunities to further enhance the alignment. To improve the alignment between reward schemes and individual needs, DA-PCC may consider offering a variety of reward options that cater to different employee preferences (Tarigan et al., 2022). This could include flexible work arrangements, personalized recognition programs, and opportunities for professional development. Additionally, regular communication with employees to understand their individual needs and aspirations can help the organization tailor its reward schemes to better meet their expectations.

➤ *Social Identity*

Table 20 Social Identity

	N	Mean
1. My gender and/or age influence how I feel about the types of rewards offered by DA-PCC (e.g., younger vs. older employees, male vs. female).	30	3.13
2.I feel that DA-PCC’s reward programs are designed to meet the needs of diverse social groups (e.g., gender, age, or family status).	29	3.34
Aggregate Mean	29	3.24

The data suggests that while DA-PCC employees generally perceive a moderate level of inclusivity in the reward schemes, there may be opportunities to further tailor the rewards to meet the diverse needs of different social groups. The average mean rating of 3.24 indicates that while employees feel that the reward programs are designed to be inclusive, there may be room for improvement. To enhance the inclusivity of reward schemes, DA-PCC may consider conducting a more detailed analysis of the needs and preferences of different social groups within the organization. This could involve surveys, focus groups, or one-on-one interviews to gather feedback from employees. Additionally, the organization may want to offer a variety of reward options that cater to different preferences and lifestyles (Kao et al., 2023). This could include flexible work arrangements, childcare benefits, and opportunities for social and community engagement. By creating a more inclusive and equitable reward system, DA-PCC can foster a stronger sense of belonging and motivation among all employees.

➤ *Social Categorization*

Table 21 Social Categorization

	N	Mean
1. I perceive the reward schemes at DA-PCC to be more beneficial for certain categories of employees (e.g., higher-ranking staff vs. entry-level employees).	29	3.59
2. Employees in similar roles or departments at DA-PCC are likely to have similar perceptions of the reward schemes.	30	3.30
Aggregate Mean	29	3.45

The data suggests that while DA-PCC employees generally perceive a moderate level of fairness in the reward schemes, there may be concerns about potential biases or inequities in the distribution of rewards. The average mean rating of 3.45 indicates that while employees feel that the reward schemes are generally fair, there may be some perceived disparities. To address these concerns, DA-PCC may consider implementing a more transparent and equitable reward system. This could involve clearly communicating the criteria for earning rewards, regularly reviewing and updating the reward system to ensure fairness, and providing opportunities for employees to provide feedback and suggestions. Additionally, fostering a culture of open communication and trust can help to address any perceived inequities and build a stronger sense of fairness and justice within the organization (Javed, 2024) By promoting transparency, fairness, and open dialogue, DA-PCC can enhance employee satisfaction and motivation.

➤ *Distinct Social Groups (Work Environment)*

Table 22 Distinct Social Groups

	N	Mean
1. The work environment at DA-PCC affects how I perceive the fairness and relevance of the reward schemes.	29	3.76
2. I believe that DA-PCC could improve the reward system by considering the diverse needs of different work groups (e.g., administrative staff, field workers, senior leaders).	29	4.55
Aggregate Mean	29	4.16

The data suggests that DA-PCC employees perceive a strong link between the work environment and the perceived fairness and relevance of reward schemes. The high average mean rating of 4.16 indicates a strong belief that the reward system could be further improved to better meet the diverse needs of different work groups. To enhance the fairness and relevance of the reward system, DA-PCC may consider conducting a comprehensive review of the work environment and identifying any factors that may influence employees' perceptions of rewards. This could include factors such as workload, stress levels, and opportunities for

professional development. Additionally, implementing a more flexible and customized reward system that takes into account the diverse needs of different work groups can help to improve employee satisfaction and motivation. This could involve offering a variety of reward options, such as flexible work arrangements, training opportunities, and recognition programs.

F. Designing and Implementing Effective Reward Schemes at DA-PCC.

The following data helped to propose and develop plans that shall guide DA-PCC in designing and implementing effective reward schemes.

➤ *Financial Needs*

Table 23 Financial Needs

	N	Mean
1. I believe that DA-PCC’s current salary and financial benefits adequately meet my basic financial needs (e.g., salary, allowances, incentives).	30	3.63
2. I think that DA-PCC could improve its reward system by offering additional monetary rewards or more flexible financial benefits, such as performance bonuses, profit-sharing, or a choice of incentives (e.g., extra allowances, vouchers, etc.).	30	4.17
Aggregate Mean	30	3.90

The data indicates that, in general, the employees at DA-PCC believe that the current salary and financial rewards they receive are sufficient. However, there is still a high demand for further monetary forms of reward and flexible financial reward. The average mean rating score is 3.90, reflecting a moderate to high interest in further development of the financial components of the reward system. These needs can be addressed by implementing a more robust performance-based reward system in DA-PCC that could include different forms of financial incentives such as performance bonuses, profit-sharing, or individual performance-based rewards. Flexible financial benefits such as a flexible spending account or personalized benefit package may also be offered to meet the diverse needs of employees. DA-PCC can further motivate employees, improve job satisfaction, and attract and retain the best talent if it provides additional financial incentives and flexible benefits.

➤ *Emotional Needs*

Table 24 Emotional Needs

	N	Mean
1. I feel that the current reward and recognition programs at DA-PCC (e.g., employee of the month, public appreciation, etc.) adequately recognize and appreciate the emotional contributions of employees (e.g., effort, attitude, teamwork), and make us feel valued and motivated to perform better.	30	3.53
2. I believe that DA-PCC should develop more informal, more personalized approach to recognition, where rewards and recognition are tailored to my individual preferences, or non-monetary rewards (e.g., verbal praise, thank-you notes, or special mentions) to strengthen emotional connections with employees.	30	4.23
Aggregate Mean	30	3.88

The data suggests that while DA-PCC employees generally perceive the current reward and recognition programs effective for recognizing and appreciating their contributions, there is a strong desire for more personalized and informal recognition. The average mean rating of 3.88 indicates moderate to high interest in enhancing the emotional impact of reward and recognition programs. To enhance the emotional payback of reward and recognition, DA-PCC can consider a highly individualized approach which could bring recognition to people's interests and values. This could embrace a system with many rewards not monetary in nature, such as public recognition, private thank-you notes, or professional development opportunities (Salazar, 2021). Developing a positive reinforcement culture and obtaining feedback regularly would further help build the emotional attachment between employees and the organization. By getting to identify and appreciate workers' work, DA-PCC can provide a better and more motivating working setting.

➤ *Developmental Needs*

Table 25 Developmental Needs

	N	Mean
1. I feel that DA-PCC’s current reward system supports my professional development, through training opportunities, promotions, or skill-building activities.	29	3.76
2. I believe that DA-PCC should introduce more developmental rewards that support my career growth such as mentorship programs, leadership training, cross-departmental job rotations, or sponsorship for courses, conferences, or workshops relevant to my role, to encourage long-term commitment and career progression.	29	4.45
Aggregate Mean	29	4.11

The data indicates that in general, DA-PCC workers feel that the reward system at present caters to and supports their professional development, but they want more comprehensive and better-crafted development opportunities. An average mean rating of 4.11 suggests an intense interest in bettering the developmental aspects of the reward system. DA-PCC may further support employee development by providing a more comprehensive career development program that would include alternative ways of developing skills such as mentoring, coaching, and tuition reimbursement. Additional opportunities can be provided through cross-functional rotations, job shadowing, and project-based learning (Shi & Xie, 2023). By investing in developing its employees, DA-PCC will be in a position to cultivate a climate of continuous learning and development, leading to higher employee engagement, satisfaction, and retention.

➤ *Balancing Monetary and Non-Monetary Rewards*

Table 26 Balancing Monetary and Non-Monetary Rewards

	N	Mean
1. I believe that a mix of monetary (e.g., bonuses, raises) and non-monetary rewards (e.g., recognition, work-life balance initiatives), would be the most effective approach in motivating employees at DA-PCC.	29	4.41
2. I would value non-monetary rewards, such as more flexibility in work hours, additional time off, or opportunities to work on meaningful projects, as much as monetary rewards.	29	4.07
Aggregate Mean	29	4.24

The scores indicate that DA-PCC employees have a strong desire for a combination of monetary and non-monetary rewards. It has an average mean rating of 4.24, indicating a high level of interest in diversity in a wide range of rewards that would meet financial and non-financial needs. Optimization of employee motivation and engagement can be achieved by the implementation of an appropriate balanced reward system comprising monetary and non-monetary incentives (Lim et al., 2024). This may take the form of performance-based bonuses, salary increases, flexible work arrangements, opportunities for professional growth, or recognition programs. This is because a package of rewards can cater to the wide-ranging needs and preferences of DA-PCC's employees and thus result in a more motivated and engaged workforce.

➤ *Tailoring Reward Schemes to Diverse Employee Demographics and Industry Needs*

Table 27 Diverse Employee Demographics and Industry Needs

	N	Mean
1. I believe that reward schemes should be personalized based on different demographic factors, such as age, gender, role, and career stage (e.g., entry-level vs. senior employees).	29	4.17
2. It is important that DA-PCC rewards programs reflect industry best practices and the evolving needs of employees, especially in terms of professional growth and career development.	29	4.21
Aggregate Mean	29	4.19

This data indicates that employees of DA-PCC look toward rewards schemes being best practices within an industry combined with individual needs. Since the average mean rating was 4.19, this reflects a strong desire for a personalized and enlightened approach to reward and recognition. To address these needs, DA-PCC may implement a more open-ended and customized reward system that considers differences between individuals and evolving changes within industries. This can be achieved through a range of rewards, including personalized development plans, flexible working arrangements, and opportunities to advance in their careers. Further, keeping abreast with current practices and trends in the industry will help DA-PCC design appropriate reward programs and, ultimately, maintain the productive workforce that the enterprise needs (Lim et al., 2024). DA-PCC can stay ahead and aligned with the changing needs of their workforce by continuously evaluating and perfecting the reward system.

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings based on the interpretations and analysis made on the evaluation on the impact of reward schemes on DA-PCC employees' behavior and performance. Conclusions and recommendations were provided based on the data.

A. Summary of Findings

The following findings were derived based on the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data:

➤ *Demographic Profile of Respondents*

The data presented in this section were the key variables with the highest percentages. The majority of employees (43%) are in the 31-40 age group, suggesting a workforce with a significant concentration of experienced professionals. The 41-50 age group also comprises a substantial portion (37%), indicating a mix of experience and work enthusiasm; The workforce shows a near-even gender split, with females at 53% and males at 47%. This balanced distribution likely contributes to a diverse range of perspectives and experiences, although individual variation within each gender group is still significant; A significant portion of the workforce is involved in research (33.3%) and technical roles (20%), reflecting a strong emphasis on innovation and development within the organization. Administrative positions also make up 20% of the workforce, highlighting the importance of operational support; A large majority (70%) of employees have been with the organization for 7 or more years, indicating a strong organizational culture, deep institutional knowledge, and high employee commitment. However, the presence of employees with less than 7 years of tenure suggests some turnover or recent hiring, which could bring fresh ideas and perspectives, fostering innovation and continuity; Overall, the data highlights a workforce with a balance of experience, innovation, and diversity, where the mix of long-tenured and newer employees contributes to both stability and fresh perspectives within the organization.

➤ *Rewards Schemes Implemented at DA-PCC*

The data reveals that DA-PCC employees generally perceive a positive impact from the organization's reward schemes on their motivation and job satisfaction, with an average mean rating of 3.88, indicating moderate to high satisfaction. Employees value opportunities for personal and professional growth, with particular emphasis on recognition, responsibility, and career advancement, which are seen as key motivators. However, while employees feel valued, there is room for improvement in recognition practices, particularly in providing more frequent and personalized recognition programs.

The working environment at DA-PCC is viewed positively by employees, and the compensation and benefits package are considered satisfactory. Employees appreciate their salary, benefits, job security, and work relationships, indicating that they feel cared for by the organization. However, performance-related incentives and long-term service rewards are areas that could be improved. Employees desire stronger performance-based rewards and recognition for outstanding achievements and long service.

➤ *Effectiveness of Reward Schemes on Motivation and Organizational Commitment at DA-PCC*

In terms of **Employee Physiological Needs**, employees generally feel their financial needs are adequately met, with a mean rating of 3.83. However, satisfaction with rewards supporting overall well-being and daily life is slightly lower (3.48). While employees are content with their salaries and allowances, there is room for improvement in providing additional benefits, such as health, pension, welfare, and professional development schemes.

In terms of **Employee Safety and Security**, employees moderately agree that the reward system at DA-PCC contributes positively to their job security and long-term career stability, with a mean score of 3.69. However, this perception is not overwhelming. In terms of their sense of security in their current role, employees give a slightly lower rating of 3.50, indicating that while the reward system is somewhat reassuring, it does not strongly influence their job security.

In terms of **Employee Self-Esteem**, the reward system is seen to positively impact employees' self-esteem and sense of accomplishment, with an average rating of 3.64. Employees feel valued, which boosts their self-worth, but there is potential for further development, such as more personalized recognition programs and opportunities to showcase achievements.

In terms of **Employee Organizational Belongingness**, employees generally feel a moderate sense of belonging to the organization, with a rating of 3.64. The reward system helps employees feel valued and part of the team, which is essential for engagement and retention.

In terms of **Employee Self-Actualization**, the reward system positively influences employees' self-actualization, with an average rating of 3.75. Employees feel motivated to strive for excellence and personal growth, which benefits their overall job satisfaction.

➤ *Effectiveness of Reward Schemes on Employee Performance, Productivity and Work Quality at DA-PCC*

In terms of **Clarity of Reward Schemes**, employees are generally aware of the criteria for earning rewards but feel that clarity and communication about the reward processes could be improved. With a mean rating of 3.12, there is moderate satisfaction with the transparency of reward schemes.

In terms of **Challenges of Reward Schemes**, employees view the tasks related to qualifying for rewards as challenging, with a mean rating of 3.74. While the challenging nature of tasks is seen as a motivator for higher performance and productivity, it is essential to balance these challenges with adequate support.

In terms of **Commitment to Reward Schemes**, employees show strong commitment to achieving reward scheme goals, with an average mean rating of 3.84. The reward system encourages focus and motivation, which positively impacts productivity and job satisfaction.

In terms of **Feedback and Impact of Reward Schemes**, employees rate the frequency and quality of feedback they receive at 3.20, indicating that there is room for improvement. Although the feedback is motivating, employees desire more frequent and specific feedback regarding their performance and progress toward reward goals.

The **Complexity of Reward Schemes**, is seen as somewhat of a hindrance, with a mean rating of 3.15. While complexity can provide motivation, overly complex schemes can lead to confusion and frustration.

In terms of **Impact of Reward Schemes on Work Quality and Productivity**, employees perceive a moderate positive impact of reward schemes on their work quality and productivity, with an average mean rating of 3.38. While the complexity of the reward system may affect some employees' ability to perform at their best, the reward schemes are generally seen as motivating.

➤ *Demographic Factors' affect on Perceptions of Rewards Scheme at DA-PCC*

In terms of **Personal Identity**, employees perceive a moderate alignment between the reward schemes and their personal values and career stages, with an average rating of 3.43. While employees feel that the rewards are somewhat relevant to their individual needs, there is room for improvement.

In terms of **Social Identity**, employees view the reward schemes as moderately inclusive, with a mean rating of 3.24. While the programs are generally seen as designed to be inclusive, there is potential for improvement to better meet the diverse needs of different social groups within the organization.

In terms of **Social Categorization**, employees generally perceive the reward schemes as fair, with an average rating of 3.45. However, some concerns about biases or inequities in reward distribution remain.

In terms of **Work Environment and Reward Scheme Perception**, there is a strong link between the work environment and employees' perceptions of fairness and relevance in the reward system, with a high average rating of 4.16. Employees believe that the reward system could be improved to better meet the needs of different work groups.

➤ *Designing and Implementing Effective Reward Schemes at DA-PCC*

When it comes to Financial Needs, employees at DA-PCC generally feel that their current salary and financial rewards are sufficient, with a high interest in further development of the financial components of the reward system. The average mean rating of 3.90 indicates moderate to high interest in additional monetary incentives. In terms of Emotional Needs, while DA-PCC employees perceive the current reward and recognition programs as effective, there is a strong desire for more personalized and informal recognition. With an average mean rating of 3.88, employees' express interest in enhancing the emotional impact of recognition. Moreover, employees generally feel that the reward system supports their professional development, but they seek more comprehensive and tailored opportunities. With a mean rating of 4.11, there is strong interest in enhancing the developmental aspects of the reward system.

The study shows that there is a high desire for a balance between monetary and non-monetary rewards, as indicated by the mean rating of 4.24. Employees want a diverse range of rewards that address both their financial and non-financial needs. DA-PCC employees desire a reward system that aligns with both industry best practices and individual needs. The average mean rating of 4.19 suggests strong interest in a personalized and evolving reward system.

B. Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following specific conclusions were drawn:

- The DA-PCC organization is made up of a diverse and steady workforce, with a high percentage of employees aged 31 to 50, who provides a lot of expertise and stability. The near-equal gender mix indicates balanced perspectives, while the substantial presence of research and technical roles shows an emphasis on innovation and development. Employee tenure is typically long

on average, indicating a strong organizational culture and commitment, which may be advantageous for the continuity and retaining of deep institutional knowledge. However, the presence of newer employees indicates an opportunity of new ideas and creativity. Balancing the expertise of long-tenured employees with the enthusiasm of new employees may result in a dynamic and productive workplace.

- The DA-PCC employees generally believe that reward schemes have positive impact on their motivation and job satisfaction. Employees appreciate the prospects for growth and feel valued, however there is potential for improvement, particularly in recognition processes and performance-based rewards.
- The DA-PCC employees are pleased with their financial needs and feel appreciated in terms of recognition; yet, there is potential for improvement in general well-being benefits and job security. Although the incentive system is seen to contribute favorably to career stability, the sense of security it gives in their current employment is only moderate.
- The DA-PCC's reward system has a generally positive impact on employee motivation, engagement, and productivity, but there are areas for improvement, particularly in clarity, complexity, and feedback processes. Employees appreciate the challenges of the reward system, as they believe it motivates them to perform better, but the system's complexity and lack of clear communication may hinder optimal performance.
- While DA-PCC's reward schemes are generally perceived as fair, relevant, and inclusive, there are opportunities for improvement for more personalized and flexible reward options, transparency and communication, and a work environment that supports diverse needs.
- DA-PCC's employees express a strong desire for a more flexible, comprehensive, and personalized reward system that includes both monetary and non-monetary incentives.

This paper explored the impact of reward schemes on employee motivation and performance at the Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). The findings of the research revealed that designing an appropriate reward system can strongly influence employee engagement, job satisfaction, and, overall performance. Both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards motivate a great number of employees. Intrinsic rewards would include recognition, autonomy, and meaningful work that may motivate an employee to pursue a worthwhile goal. Extrinsic rewards, consist of financial benefits in the form of bonuses, promotions, etc. It is important, therefore, to take a holistic approach by balancing intrinsic and extrinsic rewards to create an effective reward system.

The study also mentioned fairness and transparency in reward scheme implementation. In fact, employees can be motivated only when the reward system seems fair and transparent. Organizations should thus ensure transparency in the system by setting appropriate performance criteria and communicating them accordingly. Similarly, workgroups must receive timely feedback. A well-designed reward system, goes a long way in optimizing the success of any organization. Understanding what motivates employees and the kind of specific needs that a given organization must place in reward schemes tend to create a positive atmosphere of work, enhances employee engagement, and ensures performance.

C. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following were recommended:

➤ *Finance-Based Incentives including Salary Increase and Development Opportunities*

The theme of finance-based incentives highlights the importance of monetary rewards in motivating employees. While financial incentives can be a powerful motivator, it's crucial to balance them with non-monetary rewards to create a comprehensive reward package. Overreliance on financial incentives may lead to short-term motivation and neglect long-term engagement. Salary increases and development opportunities are two key components of a comprehensive reward system. While salary increases can provide short-term motivation; development opportunities can have a longer term impact on employee engagement and retention. Balancing these two elements at DA-PCC is crucial to create a motivating work environment.

➤ *Enhancement Through Career Development and Recognition*

Career development is a significant driver of employee motivation and engagement. By providing opportunities for growth, learning, and advancement, organizations can foster a sense of purpose and direction among employees. Investing in employee development not only benefits individual employees but also contributes to the overall success of the organization.

Recognition is a powerful tool for boosting employee morale and motivation. By acknowledging and appreciating employees' efforts, DA-PCC organization can create a positive work environment and foster a sense of belonging. When combined with career development opportunities, recognition can have a significant impact on employee engagement and retention. Strengthening the mechanism for rewarding outstanding achievements and long-term service might boost employee engagement and satisfaction. DA-PCC may continue to cultivate a highly engaged and productive team by investing in personalized recognition, performance bonuses, and long-term commitment rewards.

➤ *Diversity of Demographic Impact*

The impact of reward schemes can vary across different demographic groups. Factors such as age, gender, and cultural background can influence how individuals perceive and respond to rewards. It's important for DA-PCC leadership to consider these differences when designing and implementing reward systems to ensure equity and fairness. Additionally, aligning the reward system with both individual preferences and industry trends will further enhance its effectiveness and meet the evolving needs of the workforce.

➤ *Fair Implementation of Reward Scheme*

Fairness and transparency are essential for the effective implementation of reward schemes at DA-PCC. Employees must perceive the reward system as fair and equitable to be motivated. To ensure fairness, DA-PCC organization should establish clear performance criteria, communicate expectations effectively, and provide regular feedback. By making the reward schemes more transparent, fostering a positive feedback culture, and ensuring employees have the resources and support to succeed, DA-PCC can maximize the impact of its reward system on employee motivation, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance.

➤ *Combination of Monetary and Non-Monetary Awards*

A combination of monetary and non-monetary awards can be a powerful strategy for motivating employees at DA-PCC. While financial incentives can provide tangible rewards, non-monetary rewards, such as recognition, flexible work arrangements, and opportunities for professional development, can have a significant impact on employee satisfaction and engagement.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

PERMISSION LETTER TO HEAD OF DA-PCC AGENCY

November 11, 2024

LIZA G. BATTAD, Ph.D
Executive Director III
Philippine Carabao Center
National Headquarters and Gene Pool
Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija 3119

Thru: CECILIA C. ABO
Head, HRMS

Dear Dr. Battad;

We are students pursuing our Master of Business Administration (MBA) degree at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST). We are currently undertaking a research study titled *"Motivation and Morale: An Evaluation on the Impact of Reward Schemes on DA-PCC Employees' Behavior and Performance"* as part of our academic requirements.

This study seeks to examine the existing reward schemes, assess employee understanding of their effectiveness, and study the impact of these incentives on productivity and work quality. We are intending to incorporate 40 permanent employees or more from the Philippine Carabao Center (PCC) National Headquarters and Gene Pool, situated in the Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija. We utilize a descriptive quantitative approach in our methodology, employing a survey to gather valuable insights from the experiences of employees.

We kindly request your permission to allow us to distribute our Google Form survey among your permanent employees. We are pleased to provide you with a hard copy of our questionnaire, which includes 11 pages and 68 items, for your reference.

I sincerely appreciate your consideration of our request. We look forward to your favorable response and appreciate your support in advancing our research.

Warm Regards,

MIKEE A. ANTONIO

DEWI MARIE C. LACAMBRA

MARK REGGIE GOMEZ

APPENDIX B

ENDORSEMENT LETTER FROM HEAD OF HRMS

Department of Agriculture
PHILIPPINE CARABAO CENTER
CERTIFIED ISO 9001 | ISO 14001 | ISO 45001

Philippine Carabao Center
Records Section-AFMD
Ref. No.: PCC241119020448
Date: 11-19-2024 | 2:10 pm

Reference No.: ~~2024~~ - 11-35
Series of 2024

November 11, 2024

LIZA G. BATTAD, Ph.D.
*Executive Director III
This agency*

Dear Dr. Battad,

Warm greetings. I hope this letter finds you in high regard.

This is to endorse NEUST Graduate Students requesting to conduct their research study titled ***"Motivation and Morale: An Evaluation on the Impact of Reward Scheme in DA-PCC Employees' Behavior and Performance"***. Attached herewith is the printed Google Form survey for your reference.

Truly yours

CECILIA C. ABO
Head, HRMS

LIZA G. BATTAD, Ph.D.
Executive Director III
 Approved
 Disapproved

PHILIPPINE CARABAO CENTER
Office of the Executive Director

RECEIVED

BY: AP A-1346 DATE: 11-16-24

NATIONAL HEADQUARTERS AND GENE POOL Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. 3120 • Tel No 044 456 0731 •
 URL: <http://pcc.gov.ph> • Email: eed@pcc.gov.ph **MANILA LIAISON OFFICE** 2nd Floor, IOC Building, National Irrigation Administration Complex,
 EDSA, Quezon City, Philippines. 08330 • Tel/Fax No.: (02) 8927 7270 • Email: mio@pcc.gov.ph

APPENDIX C

SAMPLE RESPONDENT'S CONSENT LETTER

Republic of the Philippines

NUEVA ECIJA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

ISO 9001:2015 CERTIFIED

GRADUATE SCHOOL

Dear Employee,

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey. The purpose of this survey is to gather valuable insights about the reward schemes currently implemented at the Department of Agriculture - Philippine Carabao Center (DA-PCC). Your feedback will help us understand how these reward systems affect your motivation, organizational commitment, and performance. It will also provide us with a clearer picture of how demographic factors influence employees' perceptions of these reward schemes.

➤ The survey is divided into several sections, which will focus on the following key areas:

- **Types of Reward Schemes:** To determine the intrinsic and extrinsic reward schemes in place at DA-PCC.
- **Employee Motivation:** To assess the effectiveness of reward schemes on the motivation and organizational commitment of DA-PCC employees.
- **Employee Performance:** To assess the effectiveness of reward schemes on productivity and the quality of work of DA-PCC employees.
- **Demographic Influence:** To determine how demographic factors affect DA-PCC employees' perceptions of reward schemes.
- **Strategic Recommendations:** To propose and develop plan that shall guide DA-PCC in designing and implementing effective reward schemes.

Please note that your responses will be kept confidential, and the data will only be used for the purpose of this study. We encourage you to answer the questions honestly and thoughtfully. Your input is incredibly valuable in helping us improve the workplace environment and reward structures for all employees.

The survey will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. We greatly appreciate your time and insights!

Thank you for your participation.

Sincerely,

[Researcher's Name]

[Contact Information]

APPENDIX D

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

MOTIVATION AND MORALE: AN EVALUATION ON THE IMPACT OF REWARD SCHEMES ON DA-PCC EMPLOYEES' BEHAVIOR AND PERFORMANCE

Survey Questionnaire

Name (Optional): _____

➤ *Demographic Information*

1. Age:

- [] 20-30
- [] 31-40
- [] 41-50
- [] 51+

2. Gender:

- [] Male
- [] Female
- [] Prefer not to say

3. Position/Department:

- [] Administrative
- [] Technical
- [] Research
- [] Field Services
- [] Other (please specify): _____

4. Length of Employment at DA-PCC:

- [] Less than 1 year
- [] 1-3 years
- [] 4-6 years
- [] 7+ years

A. Part – I

➤ **Instructions:** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the types of reward schemes you have experienced at DA-PCC. Use the scale provided to respond.

➤ *Section 1: Motivators (Intrinsic Factors)*

(Motivators are factors related to personal satisfaction, growth, and achievement that encourage employees to perform well and feel valued.)

1. I feel that DA-PCC provides rewards that recognize my personal achievements and accomplishments at work.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I regularly receive recognition for my contributions (e.g., employee of the month, appreciation from supervisors or colleagues).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

3. The tasks and responsibilities assigned to me are rewarding and contribute to my job satisfaction.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

4. I am given enough responsibility in my role, and this sense of ownership motivates me to perform at my best.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

5. I am offered opportunities for career advancement and professional development at DA-PCC.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

6. DA-PCC provides rewards or opportunities that contribute to my personal growth (e.g., training, new skills development).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 2: Hygiene Factors (Extrinsic Factors)*

(Hygiene factors are external rewards that, while they don't directly motivate employees, prevent dissatisfaction and are essential for maintaining a stable work environment.)

1. My salary is competitive and reflective of my role and responsibilities at DA-PCC.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. DA-PCC provides adequate employee benefits (e.g., health insurance, retirement plans, paid leave) that meet my needs.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

3. I receive performance-based bonuses or other types of monetary incentives for meeting or exceeding work targets.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

4. I am given gratuity or additional compensation for long service or excellent performance.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

5. I believe that DA-PCC's company policies are fair and transparent, contributing to a positive work environment.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

6. My supervisor provides adequate guidance and support to help me succeed in my role.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

7. The relationships I have with colleagues and supervisors are positive, respectful, and contribute to a supportive work environment.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

8. The physical working conditions (e.g., office space, equipment, facilities) are comfortable and conducive to performing my job effectively.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

9. I feel secure in my job, and DA-PCC offers stability in my employment.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

B. Part – II

➤ **Instructions:** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the types of reward schemes you have experienced at DA-PCC. Use the scale provided to respond.

➤ *Section 1: Employee Physiological Needs*

(These refer to basic needs for survival, such as fair compensation and benefits that help employees meet their basic needs like food, shelter, etc.)

1. The current reward schemes provided by DA-PCC meet my basic financial needs (salary, allowances, etc.).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I feel that the rewards provided by DA-PCC adequately support my overall well-being and daily life.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 2: Employee Safety and Security*

(These refer to the need for job security, safe working conditions, and long-term financial stability.)

1. The rewards offered by DA-PCC contribute to my job security and long-term career stability.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I feel secure in my current position due to the reward system in place at DA-PCC.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 3: Employee Organizational Belongingness*

(These refer to the sense of belonging to a team or organization and recognition within the group.)

1. The reward schemes at DA-PCC make me feel valued as an employee and part of the team.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I feel that the rewards I receive from DA-PCC help foster a sense of belonging to the organization.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 4: Employee Self-Esteem*

(These refer to feelings of accomplishment, self-worth, and recognition for personal achievements.)

1. The reward schemes at DA-PCC positively affect my self-esteem and sense of accomplishment.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. The rewards I receive make me feel that my work is truly appreciated and recognized by the organization.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 5: Employee Self-Actualization*

(These refer to the need for personal growth, achieving one's potential, and the opportunity for advancement.)

1. DA-PCC's reward schemes provide me with opportunities for personal growth and professional development.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. The reward system at DA-PCC encourages me to strive for excellence and reach my full potential.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

C. Part – III

➤ **Instructions:** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the types of reward schemes you have experienced at DA-PCC. Use the scale provided to respond.

➤ *Clarity and Challenge in Reward Schemes*

(These questions aim to understand how clear and challenging reward schemes are affecting your performance in terms of productivity and work quality.)

• *Section 1: Clarity of Reward Schemes*

1. The criteria for earning rewards within the DA-PCC organization is clear.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I often receive clear and detailed communication about available rewards and the processes.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

• *Section 2: Challenge of Reward Schemes*

1. The tasks associated with qualifying for rewards is challenging.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. In your opinion, do the reward schemes push you to strive for better performance and higher productivity?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Commitment and Feedback in Reward Schemes*

(These questions explore how commitment to organizational goals and feedback mechanisms affect employee performance, particularly in relation to reward schemes.)

• *Section 1: Commitment to the Reward System*

1. I am committed in achieving the goals set within the reward scheme.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. The reward schemes often encourage you to focus on my work and remain motivated.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

• *Section 2: Feedback and Its Impact*

1. I often receive feedback regarding my progress toward earning rewards.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. Does the feedback from your supervisors or peers motivate you to perform better and aim for higher rewards?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Complexity and Work Quality in Reward Schemes*

(These questions investigate how the complexity of reward schemes and their effect on the quality of work and productivity within your department.)

• *Section 1: Complexity of Reward Schemes*

1. The reward schemes in DA-PCC are complex in terms of eligibility and earning rewards.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. The complexity of the reward schemes hinders my ability to perform at my best.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

• *Section 2: Impact of Reward Schemes on Work Quality and Productivity*

1. The reward schemes improve the quality and overall productivity of my work.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. Would you say that the complexity of the reward scheme has led to more efficient work practices in your department?

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

D. *Part – IV*

➤ **Instructions:** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the types of reward schemes you have experienced at DA-PCC. Use the scale provided to respond.

➤ *Section 1: Personal Identity*

(Refers to how individual characteristics, such as age, education, and role, shape personal views on rewards.)

1. My personal values and career stage influence how I view the rewards provided by DA-PCC (e.g., monetary vs. non-monetary rewards).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. The reward schemes at DA-PCC align with my personal priorities, such as work-life balance or financial security.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 2: Social Identity*

(Refers to the influence of social factors such as gender, age, and experience in shaping perceptions of reward schemes.)

1. My gender and/or age influence how I feel about the types of rewards offered by DA-PCC (e.g., younger vs. older employees, male vs. female).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I feel that DA-PCC's reward programs are designed to meet the needs of diverse social groups (e.g., gender, age, or family status).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 3: Social Categorization*

(Refers to how individuals categorize themselves and others within the organization and how this affects their views on rewards.)

1. I perceive the reward schemes at DA-PCC to be more beneficial for certain categories of employees (e.g., higher-ranking staff vs. entry-level employees).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. Employees in similar roles or departments at DA-PCC are likely to have similar perceptions of the reward schemes.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 4: Distinct Social Groups (Work Environment)*

(Refers to how different groups within the organization (e.g., departments, seniority levels) view and are affected by reward systems.)

1. The work environment at DA-PCC affects how I perceive the fairness and relevance of the reward schemes.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I believe that DA-PCC could improve the reward system by considering the diverse needs of different work groups (e.g., administrative staff, field workers, senior leaders).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

E. Part – V

- **Instructions:** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements based on the types of reward schemes you have experienced at DA-PCC. Use the scale provided to respond.

➤ *Section 1: Financial Needs*

(These refer to employees' needs for financial security, fair compensation, and tangible rewards.)

1. I believe that DA-PCC's current salary and financial benefits adequately meet my basic financial needs (e.g., salary, allowances, incentives).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I think that DA-PCC could improve its reward system by offering additional monetary rewards or more flexible financial benefits, such as performance bonuses, profit-sharing, or a choice of incentives (e.g., extra allowances, vouchers, etc.).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 2: Emotional Needs*

(These refer to employees' needs for recognition, job satisfaction, appreciation, and a sense of belonging.)

1. I feel that the current reward and recognition programs at DA-PCC (e.g., employee of the month, public appreciation, etc.) adequately recognize and appreciate the emotional contributions of employees (e.g., effort, attitude, teamwork), and make us feel valued and motivated to perform better.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I believe that DA-PCC should develop more informal, more personalized approach to recognition, where rewards and recognition are tailored to my individual preferences, or non-monetary rewards (e.g., verbal praise, thank-you notes, or special mentions) to strengthen emotional connections with employees.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 3: Developmental Needs*

(These refer to employees' needs for growth, learning, career advancement, and skill development.)

1. I feel that DA-PCC’s current reward system supports my professional development, through training opportunities, promotions, or skill-building activities.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I believe that DA-PCC should introduce more developmental rewards that support my career growth such as mentorship programs, leadership training, cross-departmental job rotations, or sponsorship for courses, conferences, or workshops relevant to my role, to encourage long-term commitment and career progression.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 4: Balancing Monetary and Non-Monetary Rewards*

1. I believe that a mix of monetary (e.g., bonuses, raises) and non-monetary rewards (e.g., recognition, work-life balance initiatives), would be the most effective approach in motivating employees at DA-PCC.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. I would value non-monetary rewards, such as more flexibility in work hours, additional time off, or opportunities to work on meaningful projects, as much as monetary rewards.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *Section 5: Tailoring Reward Schemes to Diverse Employee Demographics and Industry Needs*

1. I believe that reward schemes should be personalized based on different demographic factors, such as age, gender, role, and career stage (e.g., entry-level vs. senior employees).

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

2. It is important that DA-PCC rewards programs reflect industry best practices and the evolving needs of employees, especially in terms of professional growth and career development.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

➤ *General Feedback*

1. In your opinion, what other types of rewards or incentives could be improved, restructured or introduced to increase employee motivation and satisfaction at DA-PCC?

2. In your opinion, which aspect of the reward scheme (e.g., salary, benefits, recognition, career development) has the most positive impact on your motivation?

3. Are there any suggestions you have for improving the reward schemes at DA-PCC to further enhance your motivation and commitment?

4. How do you think demographic factors (such as age, gender, role, or tenure) influence how employees perceive reward schemes at DA-PCC?

5. What changes would you suggest to make DA-PCC's reward schemes more inclusive for all demographic groups?

6. In your opinion, what is the most effective type of reward (e.g., salary increase, recognition, development opportunities) that would best motivate you to stay with DA-PCC and perform at your highest potential?

7. What specific rewards or incentives would you recommend to better meet the financial, emotional, and developmental needs of DA-PCC employees?

Thank you for your time and participation. Your responses will greatly assist in improving reward schemes at DA-PCC!